

ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLUSTER MANAGEMENT IN THE CONSTRUCTION COMPLEX

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ABSTRACT

The publication identifies proposals and recommendations based on the cluster of methods of economic cooperation and their economic efficiency.

The large-scale reforms carried out during the years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan are important for strengthening national statehood and sovereignty, ensuring security and law and order, inviolability of borders, the rule of law, human rights and freedoms, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance. He laid the foundations, created the necessary conditions for a decent life for our people, for the realization of the creative potential of our citizens.

The absolute abandonment of the command and control system in the economy, the gradual implementation of market reforms and a thorough monetary policy will ensure macroeconomic stability, high economic growth rates, and maintenance of inflation at the forecast level. and served to create broad opportunities and favorable conditions for the development of small businesses and

private entrepreneurship, the farming movement.

An in-depth analysis of the development path of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the fact that today the situation in the world market is changing dramatically and competition is intensifying in the context of globalization, a completely new approach to the sustainable and dynamic development of our country requires the development and implementation of principles. In order to further improve the effectiveness of ongoing reforms, create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, implement the priorities of modernization and liberalization of all spheres of life, on February 7, 2017, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2017-2021" was adopted. In accordance with this Decree, an Action

Strategy was approved in five priority areas for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Each of these areas has specific sections on how to deepen reform and innovation in the country. As part of the implementation of the five-year strategic action plan, tactical actions were determined in five stages, and the State program for its implementation was annually approved in accordance with the names indicated in the years [1].

The priorities of the third direction of the Action Strategy "Economic Development and Liberalization" is a qualitatively new approach to the rapid development of high-tech processing industries, primarily the production of finished products with high added value based on the deep processing of local raw materials. Further modernization and diversification of industry, the formation of an effective competitive environment for sectors of the economy and the gradual reduction of monopolies in the market for goods and services, the development of fundamentally new types of products, which contributes to increasing the competitiveness of national goods in the domestic and foreign markets. It is also planned to continue the policy of stimulating the localization of production and, above all, to replace the import of consumer goods and components, to expand inter-sectoral industrial cooperation. Particular attention is paid to current development directions, such as steps in these directions, along with the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in the early stages of economic reform, privatization and denationalization of objects were a key factor in the formation of a diversified economy. During the years of

independence, as a result of further expansion of the potential for the development of the industrial sector and the service sector, the share of agriculture in GDP has gradually decreased (from 32.4% in 1995 to 17.6% in recent years). At the same time, the decline in the share of agriculture in GDP occurred against the background of positive average annual growth rates of agricultural production. As a result of measures taken to diversify, modernize, and technically and technologically upgrade the industrial sector, the growth of total industrial production and the share of industry (including construction) in GDP will increase from 27.8% in 1995. In recent years, it has risen to 32.9%. During the years of independence, the structure of GDP has undergone radical changes in terms of ownership. The non-state sector played a key role in the production of GDP, and its share has increased from 58.4% in 1995 to 81.3% in recent years [3]. However, modern requirements require the necessary methods and tools for the consistent, efficient, systematic and dynamic implementation of the above priorities. One of these methods and tools is the economic cluster.

In fact, the economic cluster is a set of enterprises integrated into a single technological chain, which demonstrates the ability to deepen cooperation in science, education and management, the rapid introduction of new technologies in practice reaches the basis of the management cluster is economic cooperation. Cooperation relations within the economic cluster are a voluntary association or interaction of individuals and legal entities to achieve common goals (production of goods, performance of work

and provision of services). In turn, cooperation relations become a technological package, a technological link of economic clusters.

At the end of the economic cluster, the raw material goes through all stages of processing and becomes an export-oriented finished product. The creation of a cluster requires the potential of scientists and economists, construction and installation companies, as well as the potential of employees of infrastructure organizations to combine their best practices for a common goal. As an objective need to improve the efficiency of economic management, the interaction of economic entities and industrial cooperation to solve the problems facing the relevant sectors of the economy in the production of certain goods, works and services concentrated. We believe that the development of industrial cooperation between enterprises is of particular importance. This is due to the fact that enterprises in these industries form the basis of the economy and play a decisive role in its growth.

For example, the construction sector, which is a real sector of the economy, has a wide range of opportunities for establishing and developing economic cooperation and economic clusters. Cooperation on the basis of an economic cluster of building complexes with economic entities can take various forms. At the same time, a large construction company also cooperates with clusters of enterprises with suppliers and processors of resources, as well as enterprises specializing in the sale of products, on a subcontract basis, with suppliers of technological equipment and components - on a leasing basis, small wholesale

manufacturers with legal entities - on a franchising basis.

In turn, certain features of the activities of economic entities can give rise to other forms of economic cooperation and clusters. Preliminary results of the study show that the development of cooperative and cluster processes of economic entities in the main sectors of the economy in the construction sector is largely due to the restructuring of these enterprises and the separation of small-scale wholesale and low-profit enterprises and their financial independence. However, this is due to the refusal of partner status.

In the context of economic modernization, a number of tasks can be solved by restructuring large enterprises, in particular:

- get rid of products on its balance sheet from structures that are not directly related to these products;
- get rid of the technological system for the production of goods and services by transferring it to small wholesale, unprofitable and unprofitable sectors of small business;
- use the possibilities of privatization of state property and, on this basis, ensure the further development of small business [2].

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that in the construction sector of the economy, the market infrastructure, including banking, marketing, consulting, procurement, trade, allows in practice to resolve issues of economic cooperation and cluster issues of business entities. The role of mediation, sales and other structures will increase. In this regard, special attention should be paid to their development. In turn, economic cooperation and clusters are important

tools for innovation, increasing the competitiveness of the economy and creating a solid foundation for the growth of modern enterprises. As a result, the production of value-added construction

products will increase, the share of exports will increase, and there will be significant economic benefits due to improved production and tender trade relations.

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